

Impacts of Climate Change on the indigenous Majhi community in Nepal

Nepal, being a mountainous, seismically active, landlocked, and underdeveloped country, faces a multitude of development challenges and, as a nation, is extremely vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, especially those related to water resources. Climate change is already being felt and is increasingly being accepted as a major issue facing Nepal (NCVST 2009; ICIMOD 2011; Xu et al. 2009; ICIMOD, 2013). General climate change trends have already been corroborated by ground-level observations from various communities, yielding a basic framework of identified and projected changes in Nepal (Bartlett et al. 2010).

Poor and marginalized people are facing many difficulties. The 2011 census listed the population as belonging to 125 caste and ethnic groups, including 63 indigenous peoples, 59 castes (including 15 Dalit castes), and 3 religious groups. The indigenous nationalities (Adivasi Janajati) of Nepal comprise 35.81% of the total population of 26.5M people. The marginalised indigenous communities are the most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change.

This study examines the impact of climate change on the Majhi community in Bodgaun village, situated in the Bhimtar Village Development Committee of Sindhupalchowk District, Nepal. The people of Bodgaun lost their families, their houses, properties and everything they held dear and important in their lives due to the Nepal earthquake in 2015. While reconstructing villages and re-establishing hope after the disaster, the issues of the impacts of climate change came into sight. These impacts are adding significant stress to a community already devastated by a natural disaster.

Full Paper: <https://weadapt.org/?case-study=22816>